

LIGHTWEIGHTING ROAD FREIGHT SEMI-TRAILERS THROUGH THE APPLICATION OF COMPOSITES IN TRAILER DECKING

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ABSTRACT

In road haulage the empty weight of a vehicle is a significant contributor to fuel consumption and resulting CO₂ emissions. Therefore, the application of lightweight materials in semi-trailer design is one avenue that needs to be explored in reducing the carbon footprint of road freight vehicles. Preliminary work has identified conventional hardwood-based trailer decking as a sub-component that is particularly suited to lightweighting. This paper investigates the potential application of different composite materials for use as lightweight replacements to conventional decks. Two different E-glass fibre/polyester (GFRP) pultrusions and a sandwich panel comprised of woven GFRP face sheets and a balsa core are tested in three point bending and then compared to hardwood decking through a material selection index. Mechanical testing has shown that the lightweight composite deck materials have superior flexural strength and stiffness compared to hardwood decking. The sandwich panel decking and pultruded decking are calculated to be approximately 40% and 12% lighter than existing hardwood based decking respectively. However, the highly cost-driven nature of the trailer industry could dictate that the use of pultruded GFRP decking is the most reasonable first step to introducing composites into trailer decks. The effect of indentation and water damage to the flexural strength and stiffness of hardwood decking is also examined to give an insight into the mechanical performance criteria required of lightweight decking in-service. Water damage is found to be the most severe form of in-service damage and can reduce the strength and stiffness of hardwood decking by approximately 40% and 30% respectively. This is encouraging for the potential application of a GFRP deck which would be less susceptible to water damage.

1 INTRODUCTION

Road freight is without doubt the dominant medium for goods transportation throughout the United Kingdom (UK) and there are no indications of this changing in the foreseeable future. Road freight transport however is having an adverse effect on the environment as it accounts for approximately 5% of the UK's carbon footprint [1]. New aggressive targets established by the UK government aim to drastically reduce the emissions of greenhouse gases (GHGs) such as carbon dioxide (CO₂) by 2050. The target is an 80% reduction in GHG emissions compared to 1990 levels.

Total empty vehicle weight is one factor that contributes to vehicle fuel consumption and CO₂ emissions. The total empty weight of articulated road freight vehicles is the combination of the empty weight of the tractor unit and the empty weight of the trailer. Therefore, by reducing the empty mass of the trailer the energy efficiency of the vehicle as a whole can be improved. Figure 1 shows the weight percentage contributions of major structural components to overall trailer mass. It is clear that trailer decking contributes a significant proportion of weight to the overall weight of the trailer. Hence, trailer decking seems a good choice of sub-component to target for lightweighting. Lightweight decking is also potentially easier to implement practically compared to lightweight chassis beams or a lightweight running gear.

This paper investigates the potential application of multiple composite structures for use as replacements to current conventional hardwood trailer decking. Different kinds of conventional deck materials are described in terms of their mass properties in section 2 and three lightweight composite decks are then presented in section 3. Results of mechanical testing of the different kinds of decking is shown in section 4 and the overall performance of the different deck materials in terms of weight, strength and stiffness is presented in section 5.

Figure 1: Typical weight breakdown of a standard 13.6m long dry freight trailer (not including trailer walls and body).

2 CURRENT TRAILER DECKING

There are numerous kinds of deck materials currently used in trailers; the foundation of the majority of these is hardwood in either a monolithic or layered ply form. The exposed surface of the deck is typically covered in a non-slip, water-resistant material. For example; half lapped Keruing (hardwood) decking (figure 2) is often used in conjunction with an aluminium tread overlay. Another typical example is birch plywood decking (e.g. WISA-Trans) which is made from birch (hardwood) plies bonded with phenolic resin and then covered in a face sheet of phenolic resin impregnated multi-layer laminate [2]. This laminate is hot pressed to give a non-slip surface (figure 2). The geometry and mass characteristics of existing deck materials are described in table 1. These decks are typically designed in accordance with ISO 1496: The specification and testing of general cargo containers for general purposes [3].

Figure 2: Left: half-lapped Keruing hardwood deck [4]. Right: WISA-Trans decking composed of a birch plywood panel and finished with an anti-slip pattern [2].

Trade name	Nominal thickness (mm)	Mass (kg/m ²)	Approximate total deck mass (kg)
Lamideck	28	18.2	490
WISA-Trans	28	19.4	530
Half-lapped Keruing	28	21.0	570

Table 1: Characteristics of existing deck materials [2,5].

3 LIGHTWEIGHT REPLACEMENT DECKING

The structural configuration of a lightweight replacement to a conventional deck can take many potential forms, including: monolithic panels, stiffened panels, sandwich panels and hybrid panels (e.g. fibre reinforced foam core sandwich panels). The manufacture of hybrid panels is particularly time consuming and costly, making them inappropriate for use here. The construction of monolithic panels is typically less intensive than the construction of sandwich panels, however, the use of a sandwich or stiffened panel can significantly increase flexural rigidity and flexural strength without significantly increasing weight. Hence, sandwich panels and stiffened panels (pultruded decking) are selected for further investigation and considered to be the best candidates for lightweight deck replacements.

3.1 Pultruded decking

A glass fibre reinforced polyester (GFRP) pultrusion is the most obvious candidate for a stiffened panel. The relatively low cost nature of these pultrusions makes them advantageous compared to other kinds of stiffened panels. Indeed, these pultrusions have been successfully laid over steel beams in pedestrian bridges, which often have a similar structure to semi-trailers. Two different pultrusions are selected for further analysis. Pultrusion 1 (figure 3) is a 40 mm thick heavy duty pedestrian bridge deck produced by *Fiberline Composites*, Denmark, and pultrusion 2 (figure 4) is a 28 mm thick deck produced by *Unicomposites*, China. These two decks are chosen to give a broad scope of what a pultruded deck can achieve in terms of its mechanical performance.

Figure 3: Pultrusion 1: GFRP 'Pedestrian Plank HD' produced by *Fiberline*, Denmark.

Figure 4: Pultrusion 2: Pultruded GFRP 'Hollow Decking 581' produced by *Unicomposite*, China.

3.2 Sandwich panel decking

There are many potential material combinations that could be used in trailer sandwich panel decking. Material selection software CES EduPack 2013 [6] is used to help identify potential material combinations of the core and face sheet that will allow the sandwich panel to match or exceed the performance of hardwood in three point bending and at the same time be lighter. Many different material combinations typically used in sandwich panel construction are examined, along with other common monolithic materials. A list of the different material combinations considered for use in the sandwich panel is provided in table 2. A material selection plot (figure 5) is created based on a beam in three point

bending. During the material selection process it was assumed that the sandwich panel face sheet thickness varied from 1 mm (with a 26 mm thick core) to 4 mm (with a 20 mm thick core). This was done to ensure that the sandwich panel has a nominal thickness of 28 mm to equal that of existing deck materials.

Potential face sheet materials	Potential core materials
Woven E-glass fibre / polyester	Balsa wood
E-glass fibre / epoxy laminate	Nomex honeycomb
Carbon fibre / epoxy laminate	Polypropylene (PP) honeycomb
Carbon fibre / epoxy laminate	Aluminium honeycomb
Aluminium	Aluminium foam
Hardwood	Polycarbonate (PC) foam
	Polyvinylchloride (PVC) foam
	Phenolic foam
	Polyurethane (PU) foam

Table 2: The face sheet and core materials for sandwich panel construction that are examined in the material selection process.

Figure 5: Material selection plot for a beam in three point bending created in CES [6]. Orange markers indicate sandwich panels which match or exceed the performance of hardwood in three point.

Because material selection here is largely driven by cost, many of the sandwich panel material combinations that are common in other industries, such as aerospace, are less feasible for use here. The materials identified as being acceptable from the material selection plot (figure 5) have been analysed in terms of their relative cost and relative mass, and the cheapest acceptable combination is found to be woven GFRP face sheets with a balsa wood core. The final cross section of the sandwich panel based on these materials will resemble the panel shown in figure 6.

Figure 6: Cross section of a sandwich panel with GFRP face sheets and balsa core [7].

4 MECHANICAL TESTING

The chosen lightweight deck materials and WISA-Trans hardwood decking are all subjected to three point bend tests to determine their respective flexural strength and stiffness. The setup of the three point bend tests is presented in section 4.1, while a summary of results is given in section 4.2. Three point bending is the load configuration that the decking is subjected to when installed over steel chassis beams, so it is considered to be the most relevant mechanical test for material characterisation here. However, it is not enough to consider the stiffness and strength of undamaged material only as decking often sustains damage in its service lifetime. Hence, specimens are also subjected to indentation damage and water damage and subsequently tested in three point bending to determine the effect of the damage on residual flexural strength. Indentation damage is inflicted applying a 10 kN force onto a 25.5 mm diameter steel ball bearing in contact with the surface of the specimen and water damage is inflicted by soaking specimens in a water bath at room temperature.

4.1 Three point bend test set up

All three point bend tests are performed on an Instron tensile test machine using a test speed of 5 mm/min. The three point bending test fixture has a span length of 428 mm and support rollers of 18.9 mm in diameter. A loading roller of 18.9 mm diameter is used on the WISA-Trans specimens, while a larger roller (34.9 mm in diameter) is used on both pultrusion types to avoid localised indentation at the loading point. A laser is used for displacement measurement in all tests. Specimen parameters for the different types of materials tested are shown in table 3.

Specimen type	Nominal length (mm)	Nominal width (mm)	Nominal thickness (mm)	Span / thickness
WISA-Trans	498	95	29	14.8 / 1
Pultrusion 1	500	95	40	10.7 / 1
Pultrusion 2	500	95	28	15.3 / 1

Table 3: Specimen parameters for three point bend tests.

4.2 Three point bend test results

A summary of results obtained from three point bending tests is provided in table 4. The average values for maximum load, maximum displacement at maximum load, ultimate flexural strength and flexural modulus are all reported. A typical load deflection curve with corresponding failure mechanisms for WISA-Trans decking in three point bending is shown in figure 7. Note that material properties for WISA-Trans have been determined for the two main material directions (0° and 90°). However, WISA-Trans is normally laid over trailer chassis beams so that the 0° orientation is in three point bending. This is because the 0° direction is considerably stiffer and stronger than the 90° direction.

Deck type	Number of specimens tested	Average maximum load (N)	Average displacement at maximum load (mm)	Average ultimate flexural strength (MPa)	Average flexural modulus (MPa)
WISA-Trans (0°)	7	8,840	12.8	68.1	7,900
WISA-Trans (90°)	5	5,840	11.2	44.8	5,330
GFRP pultrusion 1	4	28,500	10.5	232	25,300
GFRP pultrusion 2	6	8,670	7.0	101	17,500

Table 4: Summary of results from three point bend tests.

Figure 7: Typical load deflection curve and failure mechanisms of WISA-Trans (0°) decking in three point bending.

The residual flexural strength of WISA-Trans specimens with simulated service damage are presented in figure 8. Here indentation damage and water damage are characterised through the loss in flexural stiffness compared to the stiffness of undamaged specimens. Flexural stiffness is calculated from the initial linear portion of the load-displacement curves. It can be seen that water damage typically has a greater effect on residual flexural strength and stiffness compared to indentation damage.

Figure 8: Residual flexural strength (determined by three point bend tests) of WISA-Trans decking with typical in-service damage, plotted against the reduction in flexural stiffness.

5 COMPARISON OF DECKING

When comparing candidate lightweight deck materials it is of benefit to compare the materials in such a way that takes material mass, shape and mechanical performance into consideration. To achieve this, a material selection index (M) based on flexural strength is used (equation 1) [8]. This selection index uses a bending shape factor (ϕ_B , equation 2), flexural strength (σ_f) and density (ρ) which accounts for mass. The bending shape factor is a function of section modulus ($Z = I/y$) and cross sectional area (A). This shape factor is crucial as it allows for a fair comparison of the different geometries of pultrusion, sandwich panel and monolithic wood.

$$M = \frac{(\phi_B \sigma_f)^{2/3}}{\rho} \quad (1)$$

$$\phi_B = \frac{6Z}{A^{3/2}} \quad (2)$$

The material selection index is calculated and plotted (figure 9) against bending stiffness (EI) for each of the deck materials using the experimental data obtained in three point bend tests (section 4). This approach provides a systematic comparison of the performance of the different types of decking, and allows for an informed material selection given performance requirements of any specific application. The plot shows that GFRP pultrusion 1 and the GFRP/ balsa sandwich panel are more desirable than GFRP pultrusion 2. The mass properties of the lightweight composite decks are compared to that of hardwood based decking (WISA-Trans) in table 5. It is evident that the sandwich panel composite is by far the most advantageous in terms of weight saving potential.

Figure 9: Strength selection index (M) plotted against bending stiffness (EI) for the different deck materials examined. Value for GFRP / balsa sandwich is based on a calculated estimate only.

Deck type	Mass (kg/m ²)	Approximate total mass (kg)
WISA-Trans (layered hardwood)	19.4	530
GFRP/ balsa sandwich panel	10.2	280
GFRP pultrusion 1 – Fiberline HD pedestrian deck	17.1	460
GFRP pultrusion 2 – Unicomposite hollow decking 581	17.3	470

Table 5: Comparison of weight characteristics of lightweight decking to WISA-Trans decking.

6 CONCLUSIONS

Several different composite structures have been shown to have good potential to be used as lightweight replacements to hardwood-based trailer decking. Three point bend test results presented in section 4 show that the two different GFRP pultrusions examined have superior stiffness and strength compared to conventional WISA-Trans decking. The use of a material selection index that incorporates a shape factor has provided a sensible way to compare the different materials given their different geometries. Common types of in-service damage (indentation damage and water damage) have been successfully reproduced on WISA-Trans decking in the laboratory. Water damage is deemed to have a greater effect on residual stiffness and strength compared to indentation damage. The fact that GFRP pultrusions are far less susceptible to water absorption is encouraging for their application in trailer decking. Their relatively low material and production costs compared to other composite structures is another encouraging factor. However, GFRP pultrusions offer far less of a weight saving potential compared to what can be achieved with a GFRP/ balsa sandwich panel. Such a sandwich panel can save approximately 230 kg of weight on a typical 13.6 m trailer, however this will come with an increase in cost that could limit their application.

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